

ENPCS ISOLATION

Deliverable Nr 4.5-M6

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Delivery defines the protocol developed for ENPCs isolation that will be followed during NeuroStimSpinal project.

WP4 – Technical Meeting (via Microsoft Teams), WP4 Partners **Date: 21.06.2019**

A technical meeting took place on 21.06.2019 between the WP4 regarding the timeplan and the delivery of ENPC cells during the project. There are some issues related to the cell delivery to be taken care of and therefore the solution at this point is the sample delivery from the WP4 partners to FORTH and a plan for exchange of visits/training between WP4 partners.

The main points/summary of this technical meeting were: **i)** Delivery of 2D membranes (from UAVR) to UCM, Stematters, FORTH; **ii)** Delivery of GO (from UAVR) to Radbundumc; **iii)** Share of cell protocols between UAVR and FORTH (maybe the use of a share folder); **iv)** Issue on handling and delivery of cells **and v)** Deliverable 4.5 – by FORTH (end of September 2019).

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ENPC	Embryonic neural progenitor cell
HBSS	Hank's Balanced Salt Solution
Pen-Strep	Penicillin-Streptomycin

1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the protocol optimized for ENPCs isolation from embryonic mouse cortices in gestation day E13.5 and representative images (Figure 3 and 4) confirming of the ENPC phenotype of the isolated cells.

2 CORTICAL (E13.5) ENPCS ISOLATION PROTOCOL

Before starting, sterilize all dissecting instruments and spray working surfaces with 70% ethanol. The detailed description for the isolation of the ENPCs and subsequently, maintenance and expansion in a culture system is described below.

2.1 Tissue dissection

1. Sacrifice mother using cervical dislocation and wait till the hind/paw reflex is absent
2. Spray the belly with 70% ethanol and carefully cut it open to remove the embryos (Figure 1A), place the embryos in a petri dish with cold Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS)/500 U/mL Penicillin-Streptomycin (Pen-Strep) medium
3. Carefully remove the embryos from the amniotic sac and place them in new petri dish with clean HBSS/Pen-Strep medium
4. In order to remove the cortex from an embryo, place it in a petri dish with cold HBSS/Pen-Strep medium under the stereoscope
5. Immobilize the embryo with a forceps (place the forceps in the ear and eye)
6. Carefully in order not to damage the brain, starting from the back of the head and moving forward peel the two membranes covering the brain
7. After having exposed the brain dissected it from the skull
8. Remove the midbrain and isolate the forebrain and then isolate the two hemispheres (Figure 1B)
9. Remove parts of the midbrain from the inner side
10. Carefully remove the meninges and dissect the cortex from the ganglionic eminences (Figure 1C) and place it in a 15mL tube with cold HBSS/ Pen-Strep medium on ice
11. Repeat the procedures for all embryos

2.2 Tissue processing for NSC

1. Remove the excess of the HBSS/5% P/S medium from the tube and leave the dissected cortices at the bottom
2. Add 1mL of warm (37°C) complete embryonic medium (see recipe below, can be substituted with just DMEM/F12 medium) for every 4-8 brains (500µL for 1-3 brains)
3. Dissociate cells with the use of a 1mL tip, do approximately 10 up-downs or until cloudy. At this stage avoid to produce bubbles
4. Add an extra 5mL warm complete embryonic medium (can be substituted with just DMEM/F12 medium) for every 1mL
5. Spin for 5 min at 100g
6. Carefully throw away the supernatant and keep the pellet
7. Reconstitute the pellet in warm complete embryonic medium (1-2 mL for every 4-8 brains) using a 1mL tip

8. Count the concentration of cells with a haemocytometer
9. Plate in a T25 flask 5×10^4 cells/mL or 25×10^4 cells in total
10. Feed primary cortical ENPC culture after 2 days by adding 1 mL of warm complete embryonic ENPC medium
11. Check for neurosphere formation and their morphology every day (Figure 2)

Complete embryonic ENPC medium (for 50 mL)	HBSS/Pen-Strep medium (for 50mL)
500 μ L N2 supplement (gibco catalogue # 17502-048) 666 μ L D-glucose (45% stock) 100 μ L Primocin (50 mg/mL stock) 500 μ L L-glutamine (200mM stock) 50 μ L FGF (20 μ g/mL stock) 50 μ L EGF (20 μ g/mL stock) In 48300 μ L of DMEM/F12	5 mL 10x HBSS medium (gibco catalogue #14185-045) 2.5 mL Penicillin/Streptomycin 10,000 U/mL stock In 42.5 mL of sterile dH2O
<p>Haemocytometer cell concentration calculation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dilute 10 μL of cell preparation in 10μL of Trypan Blue dye 2. Load 10 μL of the cell preparation to the haemocytometer 3. Count the cells in 4 squares (circled) and calculate the average <p>The concentration of cells in the initial cell preparation equals with:</p> $\text{No. cells/mL} = \text{average number of cells in 4 squares} \times 2 \times 10^4$	

2.3 Passage

1. When relatively large but bright in the center neurospheres have formed a passage of the cells is necessary
2. Put the contents of on T25 flask in a 50 mL tube
3. Centrifuge for 5 min at 100g (repeat if no pellet is formed)
4. Discard supernatant
5. Add 200 μ L of accutase, make sure that the pellet is not stuck at the bottom of the tube
6. Incubate at 37°C for 5-7 min, make sure to shake the tube every 2 min
7. Dissociate the cells with pipetting up/down several times using a 200 μ L tip until cloudy (be careful not to produce bubbles)
8. Add 2 mL of warm DMEM/F12 medium in the tube and centrifuge for 5 min at 100g (or until a pellet is formed)
9. Add 350 μ L of warm complete embryonic ENPC medium and dissociate the pellet
10. Count the concentration of cells with a haemocytometer
11. Plate the cell in the appropriate number of T25 flask 5×10^4 cells/mL or 25×10^4 cells in total
OR plate the cells for experiments

Note: (multiply volumes if more than one flasks are passaged)

3 FIGURES

Figure 1: Cortical dissection reference images.[A] mouse embryo of gestation day E13.5 [B] mouse brain of gestation day E13.5 with the cortex highlighted in the circle [C] Diagram of E13.5 mouse brain showing the cortex (CTX) and the lateral and medial ganglionic eminences (LGE & MGE respectively)

Figure 2: Neurosphere formation in the presence of epidermal growth factor (EGF) and fibroblast growth factor (FGF)

Figure 3: Expression of stemness markers by the isolated ENPCs [A] Neurosphere of ENPCs (mouse embryos E14, passage 3) expressing Nestin (red). Nuclei (DAPI) in blue [B] Attached culture of ENPCs (passage 3) 3DIV on substrate coated with PDL/Laminin expressing the stemness markers Nestin (red) and SOX2 (green)

Figure 4: Expression of proliferation marker ki67 (red) by the isolated ENPCs. Nestin in green and nuclei (DAPI) in blue.

